

Quantum Conditional Probability Applied to Classical Waves?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec. 28, 2020

Two common classical waves are sound waves in pipes and waves on strings which may have various “end” boundary conditions. These lead to the same mathematical solutions which are often derived in terms of force or pressure equations i.e. from a Newton’s law approach. In this note, we consider the ideas of conditional probability utilized to describe quantum bound states and ask whether these may also be applied to classical systems. For example, it has been known for a long time that there is a mathematical similarity in the solutions of the quantum particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls and sound in a pipe and waves on a string. In this note, we ask whether one statistical approach may describe all. In other words, we suggest that the arguments used to develop the constant momentum conditional probability $\exp(ipx)$ in quantum mechanics should apply to classical systems as well, even though the Schrodinger equation differs from the classical wave equations which contain second order derivatives in both x and t .

Sound and Waves on a String

An equation for sound waves in a thermal gas may be obtained by using a pressure hydrodynamic equation: $\text{density } du/dt + \text{grad } P = 0$ together with the continuity equation $d \text{ density}/dt + \text{density grad dot } u = 0$ as shown in (1). This leads to the equation:

$$\text{Grad.grad density} - \text{density } k \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{density} = 0 \text{ where } k \text{ is a constant ((1))}$$

In other words, one obtains a wave equation with second derivatives in both x and t and spatial density as the argument. The result is strongly dependent on the idea of pressure or force even though one uses hydrodynamical equations which follow from the Boltzmann transport equation and conservation laws.

An equation for waves on a string may be obtained using force considerations. At first the string is taut, but horizontal. It is plucked at one point, and a force equation written. Again, an equation with second order derivatives in t and x is obtained:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} y = a a \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} y \quad ((2)) \text{ where } a \text{ is a constant}$$

If one considers stationary equilibrium solutions of either type of wave, there exist sinusoidal solutions. The question we ask is whether such solutions may be obtained strictly from statistical considerations. For example, a gas with no external potential $V(x)$ has a constant density. This result follows from the statistical idea that gas particles have the same probability to be at any position. (Other derivations are also possible. For example, if there were a higher density in one region, it would have a higher pressure by Boyle’s law (ideal gas law) and there would be a net

force which would create motion according to Newton's law. For equal density, there is equal pressure and hence a balance of forces as in mechanical equilibrium problems.)

For the situation of an equilibrium disturbance introduced into the gas, one may argue that it may affect spatial density. If this is the case, what pattern should arise? One might argue that a periodic function is the closest to a constant function. In other words, there is regularity throughout the system. Furthermore, higher density areas arise by removing particles from an average density area, so one would expect "above" and "below" average density regions (i.e. positive and negative values). One would also expect the disturbance to carry a momentum k (linked to pressure). This picture now appears to be very similar to the quantum bound case, in particular for a particle in a potential with an infinite potential at the walls.

Quantum Particle in a Box with an Infinite Potential

In the quantum case, there is no medium, however, such as a thermal gas or a string, but there is still a conditional probability. A free quantum particle is known to differ from a classical particle because it may cause an interference pattern. Thus, describing a quantum free particle by momentum p and kinetic energy $pp/2m$ does not suffice (while it does for a classical particle). Two free quantum particles with the same momentum (i.e. indistinguishable) may "interfere" if they travel different lengths. Thus, it seems that x must be part of a probability picture. It also seems that one wishes to have equal probability for the particle to be at any x point, but a real positive constant cannot be used, one needs a function of x and most likely p too. The momentum p describes how fast the particle moves and should describe changes in the conditional probability. A periodic function most closely resembles a constant probability, but it has varying values and probability cannot be created and disappear in this example. Thus, one may consider a complex probability. If this probability changes in space d/dx at the rate of p (due to the physical momentum) then:

$$d/dx P(p,x) = p P(p,x) \text{ and } P^*(p,x)P(p,x) = 1 \quad ((3))$$

A solution to ((3)) is $\exp(ipx)$ which is used in quantum mechanics for the probability. $\exp(ipx)$ interestingly is not only used for a quantum free particle with a constant momentum p , but also arises in the problem of a quantum particle in a box with infinite potentials at the wall, except for the fact that p average replaces p . Thus, x again plays a role, but it is the average momentum which describes the change in conditional probability $d/dx P$.

Classical Waves and Quantum Probability

In the above section, we argued that quantum probability $\exp(ipx)$ is based on the idea that probability must depend on x and also on p . With respect to p , the change in conditional probability $d/dx P = p P$ i.e. p controls the rate of change of probability in space. It seems that these two ideas apply directly to the classical sound and string waves. Both depend on x and are associated with a fixed momentum. Thus, one might suggest a solution of $\exp(ipx) + / -\exp(-ipx)$ for these classical cases and obtain sinusoidal solutions which apply to the bound

state. (Such a solution could have been obtained by solving ((1)) and ((2)), but such a solution would not follow from statistical arguments.)

We try to argue that statistical arguments applied to conditional probability may apply to both quantum and classical disturbance problems.

The Schrodinger Equation

It may be noted that the Schrodinger is second order in x , but only linear in t , unlike the sound and string differential equations ((1)) and ((2)). The Schrodinger equation represents conservation of energy (in the bound state case). One begins with the idea of a conditional probability for a particle $\exp(ipx)$ using statistical arguments which are not linked to a wave equation, but only to probability. One then postulates a probability distribution of these conditional probabilities at each point x due to stochastic hits from a potential with is $V(x)$ on average. This is a completely different approach than using force or pressure arguments as used to develop ((1)) and ((2)). Nevertheless, we argue that $\exp(ipx)$ as a conditional probability may apply to both quantum and classical cases based strictly on statistical arguments.

Quantum mechanics also differs from the classical picture in that one use $W^*(x)W(x)$ ($W(x)=\sum \text{over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$) to describe the spatial density whereas $\exp(ipx)$ is a conditional probability. The sound and string wave systems manifest themselves directly in terms of this same conditional probability i..e. $\exp(ipx) \pm \exp(-ipx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that statistical arguments used to obtain the conditional probability of a free quantum particle i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ seem to be based on the idea that x and p are part of this probability. At the same time, statistically the particle should have the same probability to be at any x point. As a result, a positive, real constant may not be used as in classical physics. This suggests a complex probability. It seems that the change of this probability in space i.e. d/dx should be proportional to p , the physical momentum (or to average p using conditional probability in more complicated cases). Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution. It seems these arguments should also apply to classical sound and string waves. These waves are usually described as solutions of equations with second order derivatives in x and t which in turn follow from force or pressure equations. Although there is no issue with using force or pressure equations (they are based on physical phenomena), we argue the results should also follow directly from statistical arguments. As noted, one may argue that density in a gas is constant through a pressure (force balance) with force being proportional to density from the ideal gas law. Alternatively, one may use a statistical argument suggesting that a particle has equal probability to be at any x point. By adding a disturbance to a classical system, probability becomes dependent on x , yet at the same time must somehow be independent of x . This at first seems like a paradox, but using a complex conditional probability $\exp(ipx)$ allows for x dependence and motion, but at the same time leads to a constant modulus independent of x .

References

1. Huang, K. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1983) page 103.
2. Churchill, R and Ward Brown J. Fourier Series and Boundary Value Problems (McGraw Hill 1978) page 6.